

Notes

Inorganic Compounds as Membrane Electrodes in Potentiometric Studies

M. ADHIKARI and G. SEN

Department of Applied Chemistry, Calcutta University,
Calcutta-9

Manuscript received 28 August 1973, accepted 8 February 1974

TENDELOO¹ suggested the use of calcium containing minerals as selective membrane electrodes for measurements of calcium ion in solution. Danel² showed that a large number of materials could be transformed into ion-exchangers by chemical treatments.

The object of this work is to demonstrate the use of simple inorganic compounds (obtained either by precipitation reaction or by evaporation to dryness technique) as materials for membrane electrodes. The e. m. f. of the concentration cell without transference e. g.

may be regarded as membrane potential, E_M . It is possible to relate E_M to ion activity just as in concentration cells, i. e.

$$E_M \equiv \frac{RT}{nF} \ln \frac{a_2}{a_1} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

The membrane potentials of same electrolyte in same solvent (either aquo or aquo-alcoholic) but of different concentrations were measured and compared with the theoretical e.m.f. (E_M in eqn. 1) of concentration cells.

For various membranes, the concentration maxima and minima that showed theoretical Nernst e. m. f. value for concentration cell within ± 0.2 mv were considered as Nernst concentration range.

Experimental

The materials used for preparation of various membranes were: a) calcium oxalate, b) ammonium oxalate, c) uranyl oxalate and d) mixed oxalate of calcium and ammonium (mixed in the ratio 2 : 1).

Calcium oxalate was precipitated from calcium chloride solution and oxalic acid⁴. Equal volumes of $NH_4 OH \left(\frac{N}{10}\right)$ and $(COOH)_2, 2H_2O \left(\frac{N}{10}\right)$ was evaporated to dryness in a water bath. Ca and NH_4 oxalate thus prepared, were mixed (2 : 1) in suspension and were dried to get mixed oxalate. U(VI) nitrate was reduced to U(IV) nitrate by dithionate and treated with saturated oxalic acid to get uranyl oxalate as precipitate⁵.

The materials were then dried and ground to 200 mesh size. The 0.6 gm of such compounds after being mixed with 0.4 g of polystyrene were shaken vigorously with 10 ml toluene containing a drop of dibutyl phthalate (acting as a surfactant). The resultant suspension was allowed to evaporate to dryness over a plain stainless steel plate previously wiped with a cotton soaked in paraffin oil. The film (0.3 mm to 0.4 mm thick) thus obtained, was cut by sharp blade for desired size and fixed at one end of pyrex glass tube (8 to 10 mm diameter) by an adhesive (polystyrene in toluene).

These affixed membranes were soaked with concentrated solution of the salt whose concentration range was intended to be measured. After soaking for 72 hrs. the membranes were thoroughly washed with water (both inside and outside) and tested for asymmetry potential (i. e. potential generated across the membrane on separating solutions of the same electrolyte with equal concentration). The potential developed, if any, was removed by dipping the membrane in a dilute solution of that electrolyte.

In potentiometric measurements electrical connections were made using tiny calomel electrodes (having asymmetry potential within ± 0.2 mv). For preparation of these calomel electrodes solvents of similar composition as were used in dissolving the electrolyte were used. The e. m. f. values were recorded within ± 0.05 mv with Leeds-Northrup K_2 type potentiometer and Leeds-Northrup galvanometer. All these membranes were found to be cation-selective.

For calculation of activity of the desired cation in solution, the activity coefficient values were taken from literature³ or evaluated using Debye-Huckel equation for dilute solution.

Electrolytes used in these measurements were A. R. grade KCl, NaCl, HCl, $CaCl_2$, $ZnCl_2$ and $MgSO_4$. The solvents used were A. R. grade methanol, ethanol and n-propanol.

Results and Discussion

In the table only results of measurement in aqueous and 20 weight % of ethanol in aquo-ethanol are given. Similar measurements were made in solvents of 40 and 60% weight ethanol in aquo-ethanolic mixture and also in aquo-methanolic and aquo n-propanolic solvents of similar compositions.

The experiments show that for Ca oxalate and NH_4^+ oxalate membranes the concentration maxima of the Nernst range, decreases with the increase in dielectric constant of the media. This also reveals the fact that for all the membranes the Nernst concentration range is wider for monovalent ions than that for divalent ions. Similar observations^{6,7} were made earlier when clay or resin were used as membrane materials. It is to be noticed that uranyl oxalate is not a suitable material to be used as membrane electrodes in such study specially in aquo-organic solvents.

TABLE I—NERNST CONCENTRATION RANGE (IN MOLARITY) WITH DIFFERENT MEMBRANES FOR SEVERAL MONO AND DIVALENT CATIONS IN VARIOUS SOLVENT COMPOSITIONS

Material used as membrane	Of the Nernst concentration range, the minima was kept at $1 \times 10^{-4}M$ and the maxima ($10^{-2}M$) for different cations					
	H ⁺	Na ⁺	K ⁺	Ca ⁺⁺	Zn ⁺⁺	Mg ⁺⁺
i) Aqueous solution						
Ca oxalate	2.0	1.2	1.2	0.9	0.6	0.6
NH ₄ "	1.0	0.9	0.9	0.6	0.4	0.4
Uranyl "	0.6	0.3	0.3	0.1	0.08	0.8
Mixed "	2.0	1.0	1.0	0.9	0.6	0.6
ii) 20 weight % ethanol+ 80 weight % water						
Ca oxalate	2.0	1.0	1.0	1.0	0.8	0.8
NH ₄ "	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.6	0.4	0.4
Uranyl "	0.4	0.1	0.1	0.03	—	—
Mixed "	1.6	0.8	0.8	0.9	0.6	0.6

To understand the functioning of these materials as electrodes, it is necessary to consider their interfaces. Ion exchange reaction with these precipitates seems⁹ to be remote. The potential generation across these membranes possibly stems from the preferential adsorption of ions from solution on membrane interfaces as similar observations were made with BaSO₄ interface⁸.

References

1. H. J. C. TENDELOO, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1936, 113, 333.
2. H. DANIEL and K. HUTSCHNEKER, *Chimia*, 1955, 9, 49.
3. B. E. CONWAY, *Electrochemical Data*, Elsevier Publ. 1952, p. 103.
4. A. I. VOGEL, *Quantitative Inorganic Analysis*, Longmans Green & Co. 1962, p. 294.
5. L. M. ANDRIETH, *Inorganic Synthesis*, Vol. III, McGraw-Hill Book Co. 1950, p. 166.
6. M. ADHIKARI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 40, 373.
7. M. ADHIKARI, and G. G. BISWAS, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 47, 399.
8. H. R. KRUYT, *Colloid Sci.*, Vol. I, Elsevier Publ. 1952, 175.

Phenyl Pyruvic Acid-2-Quinolyldiazone : A Reagent for Spectrophotometric Determination of Copper

MOHAN KATYAL*, S.K. KUNDRA, D. P. GOEL* & R.P. SINGH

*St. Stephen's College, Delhi 11007, and Chemistry Department, University of Delhi, Delhi 110007

Manuscript received 6 July 1973 ; revised 17 October 1973 ; accepted 11 December 1973

THE physiologically active substituted hydrazones are of immense importance for treatment of many diseases. In the last decade, a large number of hydrazones containing the atomic grouping

H

—N=C—C=N—N—C=N—

have been introduced as selective and sensitive reagents for determination of copper and other metals. More important amongst these are pyridine-2-aldehyde-2-pyridylhydrazone¹⁻⁴, pyridine-2-aldehyde-2-quinolyldiazone⁵⁻⁷, quinoline-2-aldehyde-2-quinolyldiazone^{8,9} and-2-benzoylpyri-

dine-2-pyridylhydrazone¹⁰. It was thought worthwhile to replace one of the nitrogen atoms of the hydrazones with a more electronegative atom like oxygen and thereby to improve the chelating characteristics of the compounds. Keeping this in view, the new hydrazone phenyl pyruvic acid-2-quinolyldiazone (I), abbreviated as PPA-QH, was synthesised and put to analytical use.

Cupric ions react with PPA-QH forming a deep yellow coloured complex soluble in 50% ethanol. Based on this colour reaction a sensitive and selective spectrophotometric method has been developed for copper.

Experimental

To synthesise PPA-QH, equimolar amounts of phenyl pyruvic acid and quinolyldiazine were taken in minimum amount of ethanol and refluxed for 5 hr. The product that separated on cooling was dried and recrystallised from alcohol to obtain yellow flakes melting at 240°. (C₁₈H₁₅N₃O₂ requires: C, 70.82%; H, 4.92%; N, 13.77%. Found : C, 69.83%; H, 4.68%; N, 13.20%).

Absorbance measurements were made with a Unicam SP 600 spectrophotometer and pH of the solutions were checked using a Metrohm pH meter, type E-350.

To prepare $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ solution, 305 mg of PPA-QH were dissolved in 1 l of ethanol. The stock solution of copper was prepared using AnalaR (B.D.H.) grade CuSO₄ · 5H₂O. Buffer solutions were prepared by mixing appropriate amounts of sodium hydroxide with potassium hydrogen phosphate solution.

Results and Observations

The reagent solution (in ethanol) is light yellow in colour, having absorption maximum at 290 nm, with